

Real-time Anatomy of the Cost-of-living Crisis

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Summary

The UK cost-of-living crisis, brought on by shifts in the economic landscape, has disproportionately affected many of the poorest in our society, many of whom must rely on short-term loans for living essentials. This paper presents one of the very first geographic analyses of Open Banking Smart Data, a temporally continuous source, which underpins developments in FinTech. This holds potential for understanding the circumstances and behaviours which drive short-term loan demand as well as developing fairer measures of financial precarity and researching geographic manifestations of algorithmic bias in FinTech applications.

KEYWORDS: Open Banking, Smart Data, Geodemographics, Precarity

1. Introduction

Previously, measurements of personal finances have been spaced snapshots which are inadequate for unpacking the circumstances leading to financial precarity. Open Banking approaches present a step change over conventional geographic approaches to credit referencing. Historically, geography has been the basis for credit referencing whereas this novel empirical approach analyses the geographic outputs of FinTech industry. This paper leverages Open Banking Smart Data to present temporally continuous data to flexibly match the fluid nature of people's financial circumstances. Additionally, the data is profiled by the recently launched (28th Jan 2025) 2021 UK OAC output area classifications (CDRC, 2025) which builds upon Wyszomierski *et al.* (2023).

Open banking technology contains disclosive, personal, and sensitive data which pose severe controls to spatial analysis, but this paper is evidence they can be overcome in a non-disclosive manner to better understand true financial circumstances of millions.

2. Cost-of-living Crisis: Definition

The UK cost-of-living crisis can be summarised by the prices for essential goods and services rising faster than wages, therefore creating financial strain for many households. This crisis has disproportionately affected vulnerable populations, with approximately one in five individuals experiencing poverty; with in-work poverty rising faster than employment rates (Rowlingson, 2020).

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3. Cost-of-living Crisis: Emergence

The 2008 Global Financial Crisis was a crucial turning point in the UK's economic landscape. The crisis emerged from the unwinding of a decade-long financial sector expansion that generated an unsustainable housing price and consumption boom (Duca, Muellbauer and Murphy, 2010). This economic shock drove policy changes which meant stricter lending criteria and reduced credit accessibility (Dewilde, Hubers and Coulter, 2018).

In consequence to the financial crisis, new austerity measures and welfare reforms made many households more financially precarious. The roll-out of Universal Credit, alongside below-inflation benefit increases and benefits caps, have increased financial strain for many (Rowlingson, 2020) which has increased reliance on high-cost credit to meet basic needs (Harrison *et al.*, 2022).

Furthermore, rising housing costs are a critical factor in the crisis. In 1968, housing costs constituted just 9% of average disposable incomes for households in the poorest quarter of the population; in 2015 this rose to 26% before settling at 21% in 2021 (Cribb, Wernham and Xu, 2023).

4. Smart Data

Smart Data is an umbrella term for highly portable data which relates customer data and business data which can be shared in standardised formats (Department for Business and Trade, 2024). Open Banking Data, one of the early champions of Smart Data, was created as an initiative to increase competition in the credit market by giving asymmetric information to financial technology companies (FinTechs) and big banks (He, Huang and Zhou, 2023; Karangara, 2023). Open Banking Data holds extremely high-resolution transaction data which allows FinTechs to reduce their lending risk comparative to traditional measures such as credit scoring and grants access to new customers. It relies on voluntary consent and its advent has been an enormous success (He, Huang and Zhou, 2023; Department for Business and Trade, 2024). Governmental support for Open Banking Data, namely the Payment Services Regulations 2017 (legislation.gov, 2025) and current Data Protection and Digital Information Bill, has made the UK world leading in the sector (Department for Business and Trade, 2024). UK FinTechs have grown rapidly, with their annual revenues more than doubling between 2016 and 2019 (3.6, to 11 billion GBP) and investments increased nearly 700% in that time (£524 million to £3.6 billion) (Earnst & Young, 2020).

5. Geodemographic Classifications

Geodemographics are classifications of geographic areas based on the shared characteristics of their populations, such as income and age. These classifications assign a demographic profile to each region, representing the most common resident traits. Geodemographic classifications have been widely used for the last 40 years in marketing, business, and planning, with the most common recent spatial aggregation being output areas (Singleton and Longley, 2009; Wyszomierski *et al.*, 2023). The most recent output area classifications (OAC 21) (CDRC, 2025), built from Wyszomierski *et al.* (2023), are powerful tools for segmenting between populations and were derived from the 2021 and 2022 censuses.

6. Data Source

The real-time Open Banking Data is from Salad Money, a FinTech which grants loans of £500 – £1,200 payable in either 12 or 18 months. Founded in 2018, they have used Open Banking technology to gain a sizeable market share and have lent more than £137 million, accruing over 10,000 trust pilot reviews

with an average rating of 4.9 stars out of 5 (Salad Money, 2025). The data used is particularly rich as it is geolocated at a post-code level and relates to all loan applicants, not just those accepted. The data likely over represents young people and migrants because Open Banking gives ‘thin-tile’ individuals, who are people without much credit history, fair access to credit (Goldstein, Jagtiani and Klein, 2018). This is inevitable, since Open Banking allows lenders to look directly at transaction data rather than relying on credit scores (He, Huang and Zhou, 2023). Additionally, the transaction data is already reliably aggregated into transaction categories and subcategories by the data provider, as this is fundamental to their business model, although bespoke categories are possible.

7. Data Profiling

Figure 1 Salad Money loan applicants by OAC 21 group profiles.

Figure 1 shows the OAC 21 group profiles and the extent to which they are represented in the Salad Money data. As might be expected for short-term loan applicants, ‘Established Mature Families’ and ‘Spacious Rural Living’ are particularly underrepresented in the data, meaning areas with these geodemographic classifications cannot be well represented by the data. Conversely, ‘Routine Occupations or Retirement’ and ‘Young Families in Industrial Towns’ amongst others are overrepresented demographics and therefore areas with these geodemographic classifications are well represented by the data. The stratification of the data by group is itself evidence that the OAC 21 geodemographic classifications are useful and effective.

8. Results and Discussion

Figure 2 shows timeseries of the median and interquartile range for: (A) energy, (B) rent, and (C) mortgage expenditure. Because these expenses are typically paid monthly, the timeseries uses a 30-day moving window at a daily resolution. This gives a representative and smoothed trend which would not be possible with lower-resolution data sets. As a result, we present typical monthly expenditures by spending category for any given day.

Figure 2 Daily Resolution Timeseries (30-Day Moving Window) showing Median, 25th and 75th percentiles of loan applicants for **(A)** Energy bills, **(B)** Rental payments, **(C)** Mortgage payments. N.B. Vertical axis scales differ.

Figure 2 (A) presents the median and interquartile range of expenditure for energy, an essential and historically volatile expense (LexisNexus, 2022). The 25th percentile and median expenditure for energy remains stable which suggests many have low-rate annual payment plans or are not heating their homes during winter which is a known behaviour of those struggling financially (Champagne *et al.*, 2024).

Figure 2 (B) shows significant variation in rent expenditures between the 25th and 75th percentiles (approx. £100 to £550 /month). Given the data represents individuals needing short-term loans, this likely reflects geographic inequalities and household conditions such as the number of dependants. Clearly, understanding the conditions of financial precarity requires context beyond single measures such as income. This marked contrast supports Agrawal and Phillips’ (2020) argument that measures of financial precarity should be done after housing costs. Future work will look deeper into the drivers of such variation.

The mortgage expenditure **(C)** 25th and 75th percentiles (approx. £200 to £700 /month) tell a similar, although more volatile story to rentals **(B)**. As with rental prices, it is expected that the 75th and 25th quartiles are correlated with urban centres and rural areas respectively as well as north south divides. While home ownership in the UK is usually associated with greater financial stability, the prevalence of homeowners in the data may reflect variable interest rates or the cost-of-living crisis more generally. It is crucial to recognise that the timeseries do not reflect individual trajectories but rather the trends in expenses for applicants overall.

Figure 3 Geolocations of overrepresented OAC 21 group geodemographic classifications amongst short-term loan applicants.

Segmentations by OAC 21 supergroup classifications were created to investigate geodemographic inequalities (see Appendix). These showed differences which remained approximately constant, with ‘Low-Skilled Migrant & Student Communities’ spending the highest proportion of their total spending on these essentials and ‘Semi- & Un-skilled Workforce’ spending the least out of the overrepresented supergroups.

9. Next Steps

One focus of future research will be extensive data profiling. Given the self-selective nature of the data, data profiling will help understand which populations are most financially precarious. Analysis of this kind can be used to validate and identify biases within existing social indices such as the Index for Multiple Deprivation as well as other contemporary measures such as the Financial Precarity Index developed by Ye and Singleton at the University of Liverpool which is pending publishing.

Figure 3 maps the overrepresented OAC 21 groups. While it does not show individual applicant locations, it is a non-disclosive way of using the data to detail spatial patterns of financial precarity in the UK. Comparisons can be drawn between **Figure 3** (constructed from all applicants) with select periods, for example comparing winters to summers. Detailed profiling such as this could uncover patterns of precarity currently unknown to policy makers and stakeholders.

Another of the core research goals is to create a fair map of UK financial precarity that can be used by researchers, policy makers, and commercially interested parties. It will be constructed using income after essential expenses such as housing and will have an adjustment for the number of dependants. This will be finalised with consideration to relevant literature and advice from Salad Money experts. The Salad Money perspective will specifically consider which behaviours and circumstances control loan default likelihood.

This paper presents some initial profiling and descriptive statistics for this granular real-time geographic data. In addition to real-time monitoring of the UK economy, fields of interest for future research may be gambling harms, geographic manifestations of algorithmic biases, shopping addiction, geographic price inequalities, and many more.

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Biographies

Luc Wilson is a first year PhD student in Geographic Data Science at UCL, co-funded by the UBEL DTP and Salad Money. His research focuses on using Smart Data to research the geographies of personal finance with an emphasis on low-income demographics.

Maurizio Gibin is Senior Data Scientist at the ESRC Consumer Data Research Centre. Maurizio's research interests are spatial analysis, spatial modelling, and visualisation that have been applied to geodemographics, epidemiology, and human mobility data.

Paul A. Longley is a Professor of Geographic Information Science at UCL and Director of the UK Consumer Data Research Centre at UCL. His research focuses on the application of geographic information science, with a strong emphasis on the development and deployment of geo-temporal data infrastructures developed from Big or Open Data.

Appendix

Figure 4 Salad Money loan applicants by OAC 21 supergroup profiles.

Figure 5 Median monthly expenditure as a proportion of total expenses by OAC 21 Supergroups for: (A) Energy bills, (B) Rental payments, (C) Mortgage Payments. N.B. Vertical axis scales differ and values after Aug 2024 are less stable due to fewer data points.